

Summer Placement Tasks: Review and modification of metadata

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Overview of tasks:

Examine and ammend BADC Data Entities to bring in line with the requirements of the NERC Science Information Strategy (SIS) project.

Review BADC Data Entities and modify associated data (i.e. Deployments, Data Production Tools, Observation Stations, and Activities).

Write and record a webguide to explain MOLES2 elements (i.e. Data Entities, Deployments, etc.)

NERC Science Information Strategy (SIS) Project

A Metadata Quality Report took place in July 2012, where the 6 EDC's assessed a sample of each others Data Entity pages.

WHAT HAPPENED

Each Data Entity was scrutiny to a standard checklist, the gathered information was passed on to the respective EDC so that each Data Entity may be modified in order to fit the SIS requirements.

WHY IT HAPPENED

The aim of the task was to bring the records in a metadata catalogue up to standard ready for the material to be harvested by the NERC Data Catalogue Service to ensure that all records were understandable for someone not in the field but at undergraduate level.

COMMON ISSUES

Acronyms were used without mentioning what they stood for

The Abstract described an activity/project rather than the resource

The Abstract doesn't explain WHERE, WHEN, HOW, WHY, and WHO

The lineage doesn't describe the stages the resource has passed through before arriving in the data centres

The TITLES, ABSTRACTS, and LINEAGE of 214 Data Entities were modified over TWO weeks in order to bring the Metadata up to the standards dictated by the NERC SIS project

MOLES 2

DPT = Data Production Tool
OBVS STN = Observation Station
1 - * = 1 to Multiple

CUNL	<i>Global CLIMAT Upper Air Standard Isobaric Surface Check Values</i>
CUNS	<i>Global CLIMAT Upper Air Long Period Surface Average Values</i>
CURL	<i>Global CLIMAT Upper Air Vales from standard pressure levels</i>
CURS	<i>Global CLIMAT Upper Air Vales</i>
GL	<i>Global Weather Observation data</i>
MO	<i>Global Marine Observations</i>
RD	<i>UK Daily Rainfall data</i>
RH	<i>UK Hourly Rainfall data</i>
RO	<i>Global Radiation Observations</i>
RS	<i>UK Sub-hourly Rainfall data - only to April 2005</i>
SCLE	<i>Global Surface Climate Values</i>
ST	<i>UK Soil Temperature data</i>
TD	<i>UK Daily Temperature data</i>
TMSL	<i>UK Soil Minimum Temperatures (1959-1970 only)</i>
WD	<i>UK Daily Weather Observation data</i>
WH	<i>UK Hourly Weather Observation data</i>
WM	<i>UK Mean Wind data</i>

Files in MIDAS archive

ORIGINAL DEPLOYMENT: "MIDAS Surface Meteorological Sunshine Measurements"

CUNL	<i>Global CLIMAT Upper Air Standard Isobaric Surface Check Values</i>
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WM	<i>UK Mean Wind data</i>

Files in MIDAS archive

Sunshine Duration Measurements are recorded in the "WD" and "WH" datasets.

Furthermore, both datasets contain multiple additional measurements e.g. temperature, visibility, wind speed, etc.

Therefore the "Original Deployment" does not efficiently represent any datasets which are held in the MIDAS database.

ORIGINAL DEPLOYMENT: "MIDAS Surface Meteorological Sunshine Measurements"

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Files in MIDAS archive

New Deployments were named after each MIDAS datatable making up the MIDAS database from which data were extracted

E.G. "UK Mean Wind Data, Part of the Met Office Integrated Data Archive System (MIDAS)"

Deployment now explains exactly what the folder "WM" - the last file in the list - contains, and a link is available on the Deployment page to direct the reader straight to the "UK Mean Wind" dataset.

Search for in All

UK Mean Wind Data, Part of the Met Office Integrated Data Archive System (MIDAS)

General Info

Title: UK Mean Wind Data, Part of the Met Office Integrated Data Archive System (MIDAS)
Type: Activity
Sub-Type: Deployment
Publication State: published
URI: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_ACTIVITY_f26bc4ac-d72a-11e1-b5aa-00163e251233

Summary

The UK mean wind data describes the mean wind speed and direction, and the direction, speed and time of the maximum gust, all during 1 or more hours, ending at the stated time and date. The data is collected by observation stations across the UK and transmitted within the following message types: SYNOP, HCM, AWSHRLY, DLY3208, HWNDAUTO and HWND6910. The data spans from 1949 to present.

Content

Introduction

This entity contains values of mean wind and gust direction and speed measured during one or more hours ending at the stated date and time. There are two types of measurements:

1. Wind and gust direction and speed measured over a WHOLE hour. There may be hourly gust data from SYNOP messages where the gust speed is 25 knots or more. However these will be overwritten by later input - eg. hourly climate message data (from ESAWS (Enhanced Synoptic Automatic Weather Stations) or SAMOS (Semi Automatic Meteorological Observing System)), DALE (Digital Anemograph Logging Equipment) tapes or Metform 6910.
2. Mean value of wind speed for a 24 hour period, usually from 0900 hours to 0900 hours the following day, obtained from run-of-wind.

The wind speed is given to the nearest knot, direction to the nearest 10 degrees, and the time of the maximum gust is given to the nearest 0.1 hour. The wind direction from which the wind blows, is measured in Degrees (true). The entry for an east wind is 090, for a south wind it is 180 and so on clockwise. Note that zero values in both wind speed and wind direction fields indicate that there was no wind blowing at the time of observation.

The data spans from 1949 to present, where each file contains observations made over the year.

Restricted Data Access

The Met Office wish to monitor the use of this data and require an acknowledgement of the data source if they are used in any publication. Their data is therefore restricted. The online [application for access to the Met Office Land Surface data](#), which holds the UK Mean Wind data, includes acceptance of the Met Office Conditions of Use.

Please note that the Met Office data sets held at the BADC are available for **bona fide academic research only, on a per person per project basis** (i.e. all members on a same project who will be using the data must individually apply for access to the data). If you wish to access the Met Office data for commercial or personal purposes, please [contact the Met Office directly](#).

Your application for accessing the Surface Observation Stations data will be processed within a day of receipt and you will receive a confirmation email. *Provided your application is complete and fully meets the Met Office conditions*, a web account will be activated to allow you access to the [Met Office Surface data directories](#) via your login account from the BADC WWW Browse Archive pages.

Data availability and file format

The UK mean wind data are in a simple ASCII format (plain text and "human" readable).

The UK mean wind data are available [in yearly files from the archive over the web or via FTP](#).

The CEDA Web Processing Service (WPS) allows for MIDAS data and metadata (i.e. stations lists) extraction upon user request. All CEDA WPS users are encouraged to read through the [WPS help guide](#) before using the service.

The file format for the [UK mean wind \(WM\) data table](#), describes what each column in the WM table represents.

The UK Mean wind data is updated on a monthly basis.

Documentation and Links to further information and references

The [Met Office Fact-sheet #17](#) describes the instrumentation used to collect the UK mean wind data, and also includes diagrams of the apparatus set-up.

For more information on which instruments are used to collect the measurements and how they are transmitted, the [Met Office Surface Data Users Guide](#), describes the meteorological surface data and how it is obtained in the Met Office Database - MIDAS.

Citation

Met Office. *UK Mean Wind Data, Part of the Met Office Integrated Data Archive System (MIDAS)*, [Internet]. NCAS British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2006. Date of citation.

Who to contact

If you have queries about these pages or about obtaining the Met Office MIDAS stations data from the BADC then you should contact [CEDA Support](#). Your query should be answered within one working day. When follow-up work is required, the CEDA support will carry out the work as quickly and efficiently as possible, and in any case, the user will be kept informed of progress.

Author

Name	email
Met Office	enquires@metoffice.gov.uk

Online References

Relation	Title
Tools	MIDAS Data Extractor Tool a.k.a. Web Processing Service (WPS)
Tools	Search for Met Office MIDAS Stations
Download	Download MIDAS UK Mean Wind data
Documentation	MIDAS Users Guide
Documentation	UK Mean Wind (WM) Table details
Apply for access	Apply for access to MIDAS data

Associated Data

Type	Title
Data Production Tool	Anemometer
Activity	Met Office Integrated Data Archive System (MIDAS)
Observation Station	Land SYNOP (surface synoptic observations) Station Network
Observation Station	HCM (Hourly Climate Messages) Station Network
Observation Station	AWSHRLY (Automatic Weather Station Hourly values) Station Network
Observation Station	DLY3208 (Daily observations from Metform 3208) Station Network
Observation Station	HWND6910 (Hourly WIND from Metform 6910) Station Network
Observation Station	HWNDAUTO (Hourly WIND from AUTOMATIC recording devices) Station Network

Parent Activity

No data specified at present

Sub-Activities

None

Data Coverage

Spatial coverage	Max X: 60.8562	Max Y: 1.74002	Temporal coverage
Min X: -8.5636	Min Y 49.914		Start Date: 1949-01-01
			End Date:
Spatial resolution			Vertical extent
N/A			Surface

Responsible Parties

Role	Name	URI
Data Curator	badc.nerc.ac.uk	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk

Links and Services

[XML](#) Downloadable XML version of this record

Not all information in this record may be rendered in this view. Please see the XML version for complete content

MOLES 3

Title:	Land SYNOP (surface synoptic observations) Station Network
Type:	Observation Station
Sub-Type:	Station Group

Content

Introduction

The SYNOP messages contain the following observations: mean sea level pressure, station level pressure, air temperature, dew point, wind speed, maximum gust speed, wind direction, visibility, cloud type, cloud amount, cloud height, present weather, past weather conditions, and the state of the ground.

The wind measurements are ten minute averages reported hourly; measurements are taken between HH-20 (twenty minutes to the hour that the observation is recorded under) until HH-10 (ten minutes to the respective hour), and an average value between these times is recorded. The wind speed and maximum gust speed are given to the nearest knot, and the wind direction is given to the nearest 10 degrees.

The station level pressure is recorded by high level stations only, which, like the mean sea level pressure, is given to the nearest 0.1 hPa.

Air temperature and dew point values are given to the nearest 0.1 degrees Celsius, however pre 1982 they were given to the nearest whole degrees Celsius.

The cloud height is given to the nearest whole decametre (dam), and the cloud amount is denoted by the octare value (number from 1 to 8), and 9 signifies that the sky is obscured.

The transmitted value for the visibility is recorded to the nearest metre.

Past weather conditions given in two states (1 and 2) have only been transmitted in the SYNOP message since 1982.

Hourly observations from stations distributed globally results in around 60,000 SYNOP reports a day.

Documentation and Links to further information and references

A [full range of parameters](#) transmitted in the SYNOP message is available; you may need to [apply for access](#) to view the table.

For more information on the observation stations and instruments used to collect measurements which are transmitted in a SYNOP message, the [Met Office Surface Data Users Guide](#), describes the meteorological surface data in the Met Office Database - MIDAS.

For more information about the observation stations which transmit the SYNOP message, the [MIDAS stations map](#) gives the exact locations of all conforming observation stations.

Additional [information about the land SYNOP message](#) on the BADC gives a complete list of measured parameters transmitted in the message.

Who to contact

If you have queries about these pages or about obtaining the Met Office surface stations data from the BADC then you should contact [CEDA Support](#). Your query should be answered within one working day. When follow-up work is required, the CEDA support will carry out the work as quickly and efficiently as possible, and in any case, the user will be kept informed of progress.

Operational Details

1. Transmission of a SYNOP message

In order for a SYNOP message to be transmitted by an observation station, specific instruments are required to perform to certain standards. These include an anemometer, thermometer, station observer, sunshine recorder, visometer, barometer, hygrometer, and raingauge. SYNOP messages are typically sent every six hours on shortwave using radioteletype (RTTY) and consist of groups of numbers (and slashes where data is not available). The message is decoded and the relevant parameters are stored in the [MIDAS dataset](#) and in the [MetDB dataset](#) on the BADC website.

The SYNOP message is transmitted globally on a spatial scale of 83.65 latitude to -83.167 latitude, and 179.283 longitude to -179.366 longitude.

Content ⓘ

General Info

Title:

Sub-Type:

i Introduction

With few exceptions, the following meteorological elements are measured using some type of thermometer, at all synoptic stations:

- Air temperature at 1.25 m above the ground
- Air temperature over a grass surface or its artificial equivalent
- Air temperature over a concrete surface
- Soil temperature at 0.1 m, 0.3 m and 1.0 m below the ground level
- Relative humidity at 1.25 m above the ground

Many stations are maintained to meet the requirement for accurate climate averages at a wide variety of locations over the UK. The principal observed elements, measured using thermometers, for climate purposes are:

- Maximum air temperature at 1.25 m above the ground (0900 UTC to 0900 UTC the next day)
- Minimum air temperature at 1.25 m above the ground (0900 UTC to 0900 UTC the next day)
- Air temperature at 1.25 m above the ground (0900 UTC)
- Grass minimum temperature (dusk to 0900 UTC the next day)
- Soil temperature at 0.1 m, 0.3 m and 1.0 m (0900 UTC)
- Relative humidity at 1.25 m above the ground or the wet bulb equivalent (0900 UTC)

"GENERAL"
Data
Production
Tool

**SPECIFIC TYPES of the GENERAL
Data Production Tool**

Wet Bulb Thermometers: Almost all observations of surface humidity have been made using a wet bulb thermometer though some recent automatic stations have a relative humidity sensor fitted. The wet bulb is exposed alongside the dry bulb in the meteorological screen with no additional ventilation other than that provided by the natural flow of air. The wet bulb is kept moist through the capillary action of water up a muslin wick. Where ERT thermometers are used, such as in any automatic station, the siting of instruments is the same. On occasions when air temperatures fall below zero, the wet bulb should be covered by a thin film of ice, this being ensured by the observer at manned sites each time a reading is taken. Conversion to a dew point uses values of saturated vapour pressure with respect to an ice covered surface.

Electrical Resistance Thermometers: A platinum resistance thermometer (PRT) is used for the measurement of air temperature at all synoptic stations and all supplementary stations that employ an automatic system. The thermometer is exposed in a Stevenson screen of the type described in the preceding section, at a height of 1.25 m above the ground and aspirated only by natural ventilation through the side louvers. In addition, there are four liquid-in-glass thermometers in the screen that are used solely for check readings. Temperature measured by a PRT is related to the resistance of the instrument's platinum wire, measured by means of high precision electrical equipment usually located close to the screen. The thermometer is calibrated every eight years providing traceability to the national temperature standard. The long period between calibrations is justified by the excellent stability demonstrated by PRT instruments. Electrical thermometry is now in widespread use; its main virtue lies in the ability to automate the measurement process. Electrical resistance thermometers (ERT) first came into regular use in the early 1980s at the fully automatic SAWS stations, and since then have been introduced at all Met Office synoptic stations. The instrument measures the resistance of platinum which depends on temperature according to a quadratic relationship. As is the case for liquid-in-glass thermometers, calibration is performed at regular intervals by the QA Lab.

Liquid-in-glass Thermometer: At non automated climate stations where the temperature is taken by the human observer, liquid-in-glass thermometers meeting British Standard specification BS692 are used. A liquid-in-glass thermometer, having a surrounding glass sheath, has been the normal means of measuring temperature since the earliest days of observing. The liquid is generally mercury, except for minimum thermometers in which ethanol is used. Maximum and minimum thermometers are reset after the reading has been taken, by a vigorous shake in the case of the maximum, and by tilting upright in the case of minimum.

Air temperature is measured by a normal mercury-in-glass thermometer, maximum temperature by a mercury-in-glass thermometer having a constriction in its bore that holds the mercury in its highest position, and minimum temperature by an alcohol-in-glass thermometer which carries a small index within its bore for marking the lowest temperature reached. The observer resets the maximum and minimum thermometers daily at 0900 UTC.

Screen level temperature: The standard exposure for thermometers for measuring the dry, wet-bulb, maximum and minimum temperatures is at 1.25m above the ground in a louvered white screen of wooden construction. This design allows a free circulation of air around the thermometers while shielding them from precipitation and external radiation.

Grass minimum temperature: For many years the grass minimum temperature has been defined as the lowest overnight temperature measured by a thermometer, fully exposed to the open sky, suspended horizontally over an area covered with short cropped turf and with its bulb just touching the tips of short grass (25 to 50 mm above the ground). With the advent of widespread automation and the lack of daily attention by an observer or caretaker, this set up has proved impractical. At most automatic stations the natural grass surface under the grass minimum thermometer has been replaced by an artificial equivalent. A platinum resistance thermometer is used for the measurement of grass minimum temperature at almost all synoptic stations and all supplementary stations that employ an automatic system. Alcohol-in-glass minimum thermometers exposed over natural grass are used at manned climate stations. Doubtful readings, such as might occur where snow falls overnight, are not normally reported. Long grass and other characteristics of a poorly maintained site will cause inaccurate measurements. The term ground frost used in forecasts signifies a grass minimum temperature below 0 °C.

Concrete minimum temperature: Concrete minimum temperature is measured by a thermometer in contact with a concrete slab. The slab lies horizontally, fully exposed to the open sky and with its top almost flush with the surrounding ground. Platinum resistance thermometers are used at almost all stations with automatic systems, while alcohol-in-glass minimum thermometers are used at manned climate stations. Concrete minimum measurements have been made at Met Office stations since 1 December 1968 and are mainly relevant to the incidence of ice on runways or roads.

Soil temperature: At many stations with automatic systems soil temperature is measured at a depth of 10 cm, 30 cm and 100 cm below the ground surface by platinum resistance thermometers. Thermometers at 10 cm and 30 cm are buried by inserting the head at the required depth into the undisturbed soil on the vertical wall on the side of a trench which is then back-filled. This method is impractical for the 100 cm measurement; instead the thermometer is suspended inside a tube with its tip at the appropriate depth. Problems can occasionally arise where the tube becomes flooded due to waterlogged soil or heavy rainfall. To ensure consistency of measurement from site to site, the ground surface above the 10 cm soil thermometer is maintained as bare soil. At manned climate stations soil temperature is measured by mercury-in-glass thermometers read by the observer. Thermometers for the 10 cm measurement have a right angled bend in the tube so that the bulb may be buried in the soil at the required depth and the scale exposed horizontally above the surface for easy reading. Normal mercury-in-glass thermometers are suspended inside tubes for the 30 cm and 100 cm measurements. These thermometers are housed in an extra protective glass sheath and have their bulb set in wax to slow their response while being withdrawn and read by the observer.

**SPECIFIC Data Production Tools are linked to
the "GENERAL" Data Production Tool as Sub-
Data Production Tools**

Sub Data Production Tools ⓘ

- Met Office - Liquid-in-glass thermometers
- Met Office - Electrical resistance thermometers (ERT or PRT)

The **ADVANTAGE** of creating "general" Data Production Tools, and Observation Stations which combine a network of stations with a common message transmission is the **INCREASE in RE-USABILITY**.

General Info

Title: Land SYNOP (surface synoptic observations) Station Network
Type: Observation Station
Sub-Type: Station Group

Associated Data Entities - summary

Title
[Met Office MetDB data](#)
[Met Office Integrated Data Archive System \(MIDAS\) Land and Marine Surface Stations Data \(1853-current\)](#)
[Met Office Land Surface Stations Data \(1900-2000\)](#)

General Info

Title: Thermometer
Type: Data Production Tool

Associated Data Entities - summary

Title
[Met Office MetDB data](#)
[Met Office Integrated Data Archive System \(MIDAS\) Land and Marine Surface Stations Data \(1853-current\)](#)
[Met Office Land Surface Stations Data \(1900-2000\)](#)

EXAMPLE: Both the Data Production Tool "Thermometer" and the Observation Station "Land SYNOP Station Network" are currently linked to THREE Data Entities. The "Thermometer" page is associated with 22 different Deployments, and the "Land SYNOP Station Network" page is associated with 10 Deployments.

Since many of the Observation Stations and Data Production Tools, originally created for the MIDAS dataset, are re-usable the Deployments for the METDB dataset and the Met Office Land Surface Stations dataset were much quicker to write as a consequence.

Change to the ACTIVITY

General Info

Title: Met Office
Type: Activity
Sub-Type: Activity Data Collection

Sub-Activities

[Met Office's MetDB system](#)
[Met Office Integrated Data Archive System \(MIDAS\)](#)
[Met Office NIMROD Database](#)

The Met Office Activity has been modified such that its sub-type is now an "Activity Data COLLECTION", and it is the "Parent" Activity to multiple Activities organised by the Met Office.

The idea is to create an Activity "Hierarchy" to enable visitors to the BADC website to get an idea of how a given project may be related to a particular program, which is run by a specific organisation, etc.

DATA ENTITY Reviewed and Modified in Depth

Time Taken to Complete Task (Approx)

MIDAS

3-4 weeks

METDB

2 weeks

Met Surface

2 days

NIMROD

2 days

CSIP

1 week

COPS

2 days

CAESAR (just Chilbolton data, not FAAM data)

3 days

ACCMIP

1 week

APPRAISE

1 week

Aim of helpguide:

**To guide someone through the BADC dataset catalogue,
and introduce them to the various Metadata entry types that it contains.
Brief descriptions of the type of information that can be found on each
page is included,
and the links to download the actual data are highlighted.**